

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FIBRE-REINFORCED PLOYMER THIN RODS

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Abstract: FRP (fiber-reinforced polymer) thin rods are mostly used as the longerons of coilable space masts. This paper presents experimental studies on the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced epoxy longerons in coilable mast, a deployable structure used in spacecraft. In the experimental study, test methods based on the ASTM test standards are proposed to evaluate the tensile properties and transverse shear properties of GFRP longerons. The load-displacement curves are obtained in both the tensile property test and the shear strength test. The initial properties obtained can be used to analyse the structural behaviour of a coilable mast.

Keywords: Deployable structures, Composites, Coilable mast, Longerons

1 Introduction

The dimensions of launch vehicle are mainly constraint in developing large size spacecraft. The use of deployable structures is an appealing solution to overcome the constraint due to their low stowage and high deployable volume in orbit. Many types of deployable structures have been invented or used in space missions, e.g. deployable truss structures, inflatable structures, collapsible tubular booms, and tensegrity mast. A compressive review on large deployable structures can be found in reference [1]. Among them, deployable truss masts are one of the most advanced deployable structures [2,3] because of their compact stowage capacity and superior mechanical performance.

As shown in Figure 1, coilable mast is a type of deployable truss structures and it consists of longerons, diagonals, battens, and other components. This technology relies on some full length longerons that are coiled as springs in the stowed configuration [1]. The elastic coiling deformation of the longerons provides the strain energy necessary for the mast's deployment. Therefore, the longerons are the most crucial element in the structure and they govern the mechanical behaviour of a coilable mast. Longerons are very thin spring rods, which are usually made of unidirectional glass or carbon fibre reinforced polymer [4, 5]. The mechanical properties of

longerons are fundamental input data in the analysis and design of coilable masts.

Some efforts [6-9] have been made to investigate the deployment behaviour and mechanical response of coilable masts by using different approaches, e.g. finite element (FE) analysis, experiment, and close-form solution. However, most of the work did not mention the material properties of longerons. Although some specified the mechanical properties of longerons, no details were presented to explain the determination of these values. One of the reasons is that these elastic properties are simply postulated by authors on the basis of their experience, and no experimental or analytical studies have been carried out to evaluate the properties.

Since very little work has been done to investigate the mechanical properties of coilable mast longerons, it is apparently necessary to quantify these data using scientific methods. Only in this way, the fidelity of the structural analysis of coilable masts can be ensured, and this is the motivation behind the current work.

The present paper addresses the determination of the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) longerons using the experimental method. The longitudinal tensile properties and transverse shear properties of a group of GFRP thin rods are determined in an experimental study. Test

methods based on the ASTM test standards are proposed to evaluate the tensile properties and transverse shear properties of GFRP longerons. The load-displacement curves are obtained in both the tensile property test and the shear strength test.

Figure 1 A three dimensional model of a coilable mast.

2 Experimental Studies

At present, standard test methods for mechanical properties of GFRP thin rod are not available in the aerospace industry. However in civil engineering, there are standard test methods [10, 11] for tensile and transverse shear strength of FRP bars, which are normally used as tensile elements in reinforced, prestressed, or post-tensioned concrete. The current test setups and test procedures to measure tensile and shear properties of a group of GFRP thin rods have been made based on the regulations of ASTM D7205/D7205M-06 [10], which is for tensile properties of FRP composite bars, and ASTM D7617/D7617M-11 [11], which is for shear strength of FRP bars.

2.1 Test Specimen

Four groups (A, B, C and D) of test specimens, made of different types of GFRP thin rods, have been tested. Groups A and D have a circular cross section, while groups B and C have a rectangular cross section. In a tensile property test, a specimen is usually of dog-bone shape, in which the central portion (gage portion) of the length is of smaller cross section than the end portions. However, in the current tensile test, the specimens were not made in such a way because the cross sections of specimens are already very small and it is extremely difficult to

make it a dog-bone shape. Figure 2 shows the photos of the four groups of specimens. Table 1 lists the configurations of all the test specimens.

Figure 2 Photograph of four groups of test specimens A, B, C and D.

Table 1 Configurations of test specimens

Group	Cross Sections		Tensile Test		Shear Test	
	Shape	Size (mm)	Length (mm)	QTY.	Length (mm)	QTY.
A	●	R = 4.1	-	-	225	5
B	■	5.89×7.81	300	3	225	5
C	■	5.89×8.02	300	3	225	5
D	●	R = 5.93	240	3	-	-

2.2 Tensile Property Test

A universal testing machine Shimadzu AG-X/250 has been used in the tensile and shear tests to apply tensile and compressive forces, respectively. The Shimadzu AG-X/250 has a maximum load capacity of 250kN and its test force precision is within $\pm 0.5\%$ of indicated test force. Test speed ranges from 0.0005 mm/min to 500mm/min.

A general purpose Epsilon extensometer was used to measure the axial tensile displacement in the tensile test. The gauge length is 50mm and the maximum measuring strain is 50%.

2.3 Transverse Shear Strength Test

As shown in Figure 3, the specimen is placed in the self-aligning grips of the testing machine. The grips were tightened to prevent slippage between the grip face and the specimen. In order to produce tensile failure within 1 to 10 minutes [10], a testing speed of 1mm/min was used to apply displacement control load. The lower head of the test machine is stationary and the upper head is movable. The extensometer was placed to the central portion of the specimen at the beginning of the test. It was then

removed, when the stress measured approached a certain value (550-700MPa), to avoid any potential damage caused by specimen failure. The test procedure was applied for each specimen, and the data were automatically recorded at a frequency of 100 Hz.

Figure 3 Photograph of the tensile property test setup.

Figure 4 shows the measured load-displacement curves of the entire loading history for the three specimens in Groups B, C and D. The initial slopes of the curves are approximately constant. The slopes decrease slightly and then maintain constant again. The ultimate loads of the specimens are marked at the peaks of the curves in Figure 4. Some kinks appear at the early stage of the post-failure curves. In general, all the specimens display a very similar load-displacement pattern, which is a typical response of brittle materials. It is worth saying that each small kink before the peaks results from the pause of the loading, where the extensometer was removed to avoid any damage caused by the sudden tensile failure.

Figure 5 plots the stress (and load)-strain curves derived from the displacements measured by the extensometer and the force data. In order to distinguish the three curves, lines for specimens 2 and 3 have been horizontally offset 0.1% and 0.2% respectively to the right side. Unlike the nonlinear behaviour of their load-displacement curves shown in Figure 4, the stress-strain relations are approximately linear for the whole curve.

Figure 4 Measured load-displacement curves of specimens in the tensile property test: (a) Group B, (b) Group C, and (c) Group D.

By averaging the data shown in Figures 4 and 5, Table 2 summarises the axial loading capacity, axial strength, and initial Young's modulus of each test group. Group B has the highest axial loading capacity, and Group D's axial strength and initial Young's modulus are far superior.

Figure 5 Measured stress-strain curves of specimens in the tensile property test: (a) Group B, (b) Group C, and (c) Group D.

Table 2 Measured data in the tensile property test

Group	Axial loading capacity (kN)	Axial strength (MPa)	Initial Young's modulus (GPa)
B	36.254	788.12	54.378
C	29.462	623.71	46.562
D	25.738	931.92	59.145

Figure 6 shows the failure modes of representative specimens in each group. It can be seen that the composite rods are split into many slices due to fibre/matrix interface debonding. Fibre fractures can also be seen, but it is not the dominated failure phenomenon. The mixed failure mode indicates that the tensile capacities of the specimens might be higher than the measured data because the debonding is probably initiated by the stress concentrations at the gripping area. Therefore, the test data can only be used as the lower bond of the tensile capacities.

Figure 6 Failure modes observed in the tensile property test: (a) Group B, (b) Group C, (c) Group D.

2.4 Transverse shear strength test

The transverse shear strength test is more complicated than the tensile test. In accordance to ASTM D7617/D7617M-11 [11], two sets of test fixtures have been developed for circular and rectangular rods, respectively. As shown in Figures 7 and 8, the transverse shear fixture for the circular rods consists of two rod seats, two lower blades, and two guides machined from steel. These parts are bolted together with two threaded rods with washers and nuts. The upper blade is loose, and is fit onto the rod prior to testing. Straps are used to clamp the rod firmly into the rod seats during testing. Socket-head cap screws pass through threads in the straps and clamp the specimens onto the rod seats [11]. For the rectangular rods, the round slots of the upper and lower blades were machined to be rectangular slots to fit the specimen. Two fill blocks were also machined to fit the gap between the V-shaped rod beds and the rectangular rods. As shown in Figure 8, fill blocks with the cross section of isosceles triangle are along the whole length of the rod beds. By using the fill blocks, the rod beds for round rods can also be used for rectangular rods.

The procedure of the shear strength test is as follows [11]: (1) Centre the specimen within the shear fixture and rest it against the rod seats and lower blades; (2) Insert and hand-tighten two set screws in one strap so that one end of the rod is clamped by

the two screws pressing onto the rod, through the two end holes in the straps. Hand-tighten one set screw in the other strap through the centre hole to clamp the opposite end of the rod; (3) Place the upper blade into place and ensure that the blade is in full contact with the rod; (4) As shown in Figure 9, centre the fixture in the universal testing machine; (5) Preload the universal testing machine and then apply force uniformly at the rate of 1mm/min; (6) Set the testing machine to record the force and displacement data at a frequency of 10 Hz and monitor force-displacement curves continuously.

Figure 9 Photograph of the test setup for transverse shear strength test

Figure 7 Schematic drawing of transverse shear fixture assembled [11].

Figure 8 Photographs of the transverse shear fixture: (a) assembled fixture with sheared specimen and (2) disassembled fixture[11].

Figure 10 shows the measured load-displacement curves of the specimens in Groups A, B and C. In comparison with the tensile load-displacement curves in Figure 4, the nonlinearity of these curves is more severe. In Figure 10 (a), the curve of JA-2 is significantly different to the others. This indicates that the specimen JA-2 may have initial defects, and therefore its experimental results were not considered in the data analysis. Apart from the JA-2 curve, all other specimens in each group display very similar load-displacement behaviour. Although the peak loads are different in Figures 10(a), 10(b), and 10(c), their corresponding displacements are near 1.0 mm, which implies that the shearing failure strain of the specimens is approximately identical.

By averaging the data shown in Figure 10, the transverse shearing capacity, transverse shear strength and transverse shear stiffness are listed in Table 3. The transverse shear stiffness in Table 3 is the fitted slope of load-displacement curves between certain load range, in which the curves are approximately linear. The load range for each group is noted in the bracket of the last column.

Table 3 Measured transverse shear properties of test groups

Group	Transverse shearing capacity (kN)	Transverse shear strength (MPa)	Transverse shear stiffness (kN/m) (kN)
A	7.909	285.44	15.805 (2.2-5.5)
B	23.313	253.41	26.152 (10-20)
C	19.137	202.72	24.574 (7.5-17.5)

Figure 10 Measured load-displacement curves of specimens in the shear strength test: (a) Group A, (b) Group B, and (c) Group C.

In the shear strength test, a specimen was cut into three segments by the two shearing planes. Figure 11 shows fracture modes of the failed cross sections. Each failed section is divided by a step into two fracture planes. This demonstrates that the section is not only under shearing, but also under bending. To

satisfy the equilibrium, the compressive area above the step is nearly equal to the tensile area below. However, the effects of bending on the transverse shear behaviour are believed to be moderate since the neighbouring faces of the upper and lower blades are almost in contact and the step depth is not very deep. During the test, two loud bangs were heard at the moment, when the load is at the peak and the load is at the kink on the post-failure curve. This implies that the failure of the two shearing planes took place at the two corresponding phases, respectively.

Figure 11 Photographs of cross-sectional failure modes observed in the shear strength test: (a) Group A, (b) Group B, (c) Group C.

2.5 Selection of GFRP rods

According to the test results summarized in Tables 2 and 3, the mechanical behaviour of Group B is generally better than that of others. Hence Group B is a favourite candidate in the engineering applications and it is then selected to carry out further research.

3 Conclusions

In this paper, experimental studies on the mechanical properties of GFRP thin rods for coilable mast longerons have been carried out:

- (1) In the experimental study, the tensile properties and transverse shear behaviour of GFRP longerons were tested. To the author's best knowledge, the experimental data of GFRP thin rods are reported for the first time in the literature.
- (2) The initial material properties can be used as input data to analyse the structural behaviour of a coilable mast. The test data of tensile behaviour and shear strength can be used as benchmarks for validating new models.

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References

- [1] Liug L, Barton A, Rando N. A review on large deployable structures for astrophysics missions. *Acta Astronautica*, 2010, 67(1–2): 12–26
- [2] Kent Joosten B. Preliminary assessment of artificial gravity impacts to deep-space vehicle design. *NASA report*, JSC-63743, 2007
- [3] Liu Z, Li B, Cheng G. Review of deployable truss masts for space application (in Chinese). *Chinese Space Science and Technology*, 2011, 2: 32–38
- [4] Murphy D M, Macy B D. Demonstration of a 10-m solar sail system. 45th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ACS *Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*. 19–22 April 2004, Palm Springs, California, US.
- [5] Yokota R. Chapter 5 High performance polymers and advanced composites for space application. In: *Aerospace Materials*. Edited by Cantor B, Grant P, Assender H. Taylor & Francis 2001.
- [6] McEachen M E, Trautt T A, Murphy D M. The ST8 SAILMAST validation experiment. 46th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ACS *Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*. 18–21 April 2005, Austin, Texas, US.
- [7] Chen T, Wang J T. Modeling of triangular lattice space structures with curved battens. *Journal of Space and Rockets*, 2007, 44(3): 538–544
- [8] Hillebrandt M, Straubel M, Hühne C, Wiedemann M. A new deployable truss for gossamer space structures. 53th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ACS *Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*. 23–26 April 2012, Honolulu, Hawaii, US.
- [9] Ge D M, Chen W J, Fu G Y, Dong S L. Buckling theoretic analysis of coilable hinged extendible/retractable space mast (in Chinese). *Engineering Mechanics*, 2008, 25(6): 176–180.
- [10] ASTM D7205/D7205M-06. Standard test method for tensile properties of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite bars. *ASTM International*, Pennsylvania, US. March 2006
- [11] ASTM D7617/D7617M-11. Standard test method for transverse shear strength of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite bars. *ASTM International*, Pennsylvania, US. March 2011
- [12] Blacklock M, Hayhurst DR. Initial elastic properties of unidirectional ceramic matrix composite fiber tows. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*. 2012. 79(5): 051020.
- [13] Kaddour AS, Hilton MJ. Input data for test cases used in benchmarking triaxial failure theories of composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*. 2012. 46(19-20): 2295-2312.
- [14] Ye J, Zhang D. Prediction of failure envelopes and stress strain curves of fiber composite laminates under triaxial loads. *Journal of Composite Materials*. 2012. 46(19-20): 2417-2430.
- [15] ABAQUS User Manual, 2006. Version 6.6., SIMULIA, Providence, RI.
- [16] Halpin J C, Kardos J L. The Halpin-Tsai Equations: A Review. *Polymer Engineering and Science* 1976. 6(5): 344-352.